

glossy black, with yellow basal antennal segments, yellow-brown apices of femora, tibiae, and tarsi (see figure). The pronota are smoothly punctated and

each elytron has 10 longitudinal rows of minute pits. The tibiae of the third pair of legs possess a small apophysis along

the mid-dorsum, dorsolateral combs of hairs near the apical half, and a tooth at the apices. ♂

Granulosis of the rice brown semilooper *Mocis frugalis*

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Rice brown semilooper *M. frugalis* (Fab.) (Lep: Noctuidae) is one of a complex of tropical lepidopterous rice pests. It occurs in flooded rice, but is more abundant in upland rice.

M. frugalis populations seldom occur in damaging levels because they are inhibited by natural parasites, predators, and diseases.

We collected last-instar *M. frugalis* larvae that were infected with a virus disease from a lowland field near Roxas, Palawan, Philippines. Diseased larvae were lemon yellow with swollen abdominal segments (Fig. 1). At later disease stages, the larvae turned dark and milky-white fluid oozed through the integument. Examination of the fluid with a phase contrast microscope showed refractive granules with Brownian movement.

Diseased larvae were macerated in distilled water with a glass homogenizer for further identification and purification. The suspension was filtered through cotton wool and centrifuged for 30 min to remove the bacteria. The precipitate was washed three times with distilled water to obtain a crude extract.

1. Larva of *Mocis frugalis* (Fab.) infected with granulosis virus.

2. Electron micrograph of capsules of *Mocis frugalis* stained with 2% phosphotungstic acid (X 27,600). a =an aberrant, sickleform capsule.

3. Virion released from the capsule after 2 h treatment with 0.05 M NaCO_3 + 0.17 M NaCl at room temperature. (X 22,380). c = empty capsule, rv = released virion, v = virion in the capsule.

The extract was layered on a 20–70% (V/V) glycerol gradient, then centrifuged at 10,000 rev/min for 15 min in a Beckman SW 27 rotor. The virus was collected at the 35–40% glycerol band. These bands were centrifuged at 12,000 rev/min for 20 min using a Beckman Mod. L5-65 and the resulting pellet was resuspended in a small amount of water.

The virus suspension was layered on 30–65% (W/W) linear sucrose density

gradient then centrifuged at 25,000 rev/min for 90 min. The band was collected at 55% sucrose band and centrifuged again at 20,000 rev/min for 30 min. The pellet was collected, diluted with water, and the process was repeated.

After centrifugation, the purified virus capsules were resuspended in water and centrifuged at 12,000 rev/min for 20 min to form a precipitate. A small amount of the virus capsule suspension was stained in a grid for 1 min with 2% phosphotungstic acid (PTA) for electron microscope examination.

The capsules were ellipsoidal, but an aberrant sickle-form also was observed (Fig. 2). Capsules were 433 nm long and 243 nm wide. Each capsule contained a single virion (nucleocapsid). A single rod-shaped virion typical of granulosis was embedded in a capsule (Fig. 3). They averaged 301 nm long and 83 nm wide. The virions were negatively stained with 2% PTA.

Virions in the capsules were obtained after treatment on the slide with equal volume of 0.05 M NaCO_3 + 0.17 M NaCl at room temperature. The protein capsule dissolved after 2 h of gentle stirring, but the virions were released after more than 3 h.

The disease was identified as granulosis. This is the first report of it attacking *M. frugalis*. ♂

Effect of neem product foliar sprays on rice pests

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We studied the effect of foliar spraying of three neem products on the incidence of rice pests in two field experiments at PES in Tirur. The 1984–85 trials comprised five treatments replicated four times and laid out in a simple

Treatment	Quantity/ha per round	Navarai 1984-85			Sornavari 1985			
		GLH (no./hill)	Grasshopper (%)	Grain yield (t/ha)	GLH mortality (%)	GM silver shoots (%)	SB whiteheads (%)	Grain yield (t/ha)
Neem seed kernel extract, 2%	10 kg	1.9 (1.39) a	9.4 (17.83) b	5.8 a	58.9 (50.07) b	7.2 (15.57) a	25.0 (29.98) bc	6.6
Neem cake extract, 5%	25 kg	2.7 (1.65) b	8.9 (17.33) ab	4.9 b	45.2 (42.24) c	8.3 (16.74) b	25.9 (31.60) cd	6.0
Neem leaf extract, 5%	25 kg	2.4 (1.54) ab	5.9 (14.05) a	5.1 b	66.6 (54.71) a	8.8 (17.25) b	22.3 (28.15) b	6.2
Phosphamidon 100 EC	500 ml	2.9 (1.70) b	9.8 (18.22) b	5.4 ab	63.6 (52.90) a	13.0 (21.13) c	12.5 (20.65) a	6.3
Control	—	4.7 (2.17) c	15.5 (23.21) c	5.1 b	10.9 (19.28) d	29.2 (32.71) d	30.4 (33.46) d	5.7
CD		(0.30)	(3.68)	0.59	(2.33)	(1.05)	(2.80)	ns

^aFigures in parentheses are transformed values.

randomized block design. Twenty-five-day-old seedlings of TM8089 and TKM 9 were planted in 3- × 3-m plots at 20- × 10-cm spacing. These were fertilized with 100-50-50 kg NPK/ha. Three spray applications were made 15, 30, and 45 d after transplanting. Infestations by green leafhopper (GLH), stem borer (SB), gall

midge (GM), and grasshoppers were assessed at periodic intervals. Data on pest incidence and grain yield were analyzed statistically.

Results indicated that the neem products effectively controlled the major rice pests and were even superior to phosphamidon in controlling GM,

GLH, and grasshoppers (see table). However, phosphamidon was superior to neem products in controlling SB. Plots sprayed with 2% neem seed kernel extract had the highest grain yields of 5.8 and 6.6 t/ha in navarai and sornavari seasons, respectively. *ℓ*

Effect of neem oil on germination and sporulation of the entomogenous fungus *Metarhizium anisopliae*

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Entomogenous fungi are important biological control agents that can infect insect pests and reduce their populations. We are evaluating them for possible control of brown planthopper *Nilaparvata lugens* and black bug *Scotinophara coarctata*. However, the effectiveness of naturally occurring and artificially applied fungi may be seriously affected by chemical applications.

We sought to determine the effect of neem oil on the germination and sporulation of *Metarhizium anisopliae*, an entomopathogenic fungus that infects several important rice insect pests.

Conidia germination was observed in a liquid medium (1% saccharose/1% yeast extract) with 0, 5, 50, and 95%

Inhibitory effect of neem oil on germination and sporulation of *M. anisopliae*.

neem oil. Each treatment had five replications. Small amounts of conidia were added to the medium, which then was incubated for 24 h in vials on a rotary shaker. Germination was evaluated under a microscope.

Mycelium sporulation was studied by soaking dry mycelium particles in

concentrations of neem oil similar to those of the germination experiment. The particles were incubated on moist filter paper in petri dishes. Evaluation was concurrent with completion of sporulation in the control treatment (no neem oil).

Virtually all the mycelium particles